

Research ethics & bioethics at Uppsala University 2024

Annual report from the Centre for Research Ethics
& Bioethics (CRB) at Uppsala University

uu.se/crb

UPPSALA
UNIVERSITET

About the Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB)

The Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB) explores current ethical issues through philosophical, empirical, and normative approaches. Our work builds capacity and contributes to the knowledge base for research & innovation, policy, management and clinical practice.

CRB is an interfaculty centre that is governed by a board of University representatives and led by a Director. The Centre is administratively associated with the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences at the Faculty of Medicine, where all Centre staff are employed. At the Department level, Niklas Juth, Professor in Clinical Medical Ethics serves as a research group leader and answers to the Department board. The Centre is led by Director Stefan Eriksson, Associate Professor and Senior Lecturer in Research Ethics, who answers to the Centre's board. Both roles are supported by Coordinator Josepine Fernow.

This report was written by Josepine Fernow, with contributions from Fanny Klingvall, Isak Klerck, Johanna Dyrblom, Niklas Juth & Stefan Eriksson.

Uppsala University diary number: Pubcare 2025/94

Contents of this report

Research at the Centre	3
Our approach to teaching ethics	3
Societal engagement	4
The Centre in numbers	4
Internal funding mechanisms	5
Centre activities for disciplinary domains	6
Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics	8
External research funding	9
Communication & dissemination	10
Our outreach in numbers	10
Want to know more?	11

Research at the Centre

We identify and explore current ethical issues through conceptual, normative, and empirical approaches. Our research is both fundamental and applied: providing conceptual tools and hands-on guidance for stakeholders in research, policy, clinical practice, and beyond, in six areas:

Healthcare, public health & professional

ethics: Focusing on ethical issues raised in clinical practice and care, preventive programmes, and healthcare management. Examining policy, organisation, professional roles and value conflicts.

Biomedicine, biobanks & genomics:

Focusing on the ethical and societal aspects of genetic genomic data collection, storage and use in biobank and registry studies, and the translation of biomedical research results into clinical applications.

Research ethics & academic integrity:

Focusing on value conflicts and ethical issues related to research practice: providing a bridge from research ethics to academic integrity by guiding informed consent, academic publishing, and good research practice.

Brain, consciousness & artificial intelligence:

Focusing on ethical, social and philosophical questions raised by artificial intelligence, neuroscience and brain research, consciousness and cognition, and the idea and use of digital twins.

Food, medicine & environment:

Focusing on the value conflicts and ethical dilemmas that we experience as individuals, patients and professionals in relation to what we eat, the medicines we use, and where we live.

Policy, engagement & communication:

Focusing on current ethical issues together with stakeholders. Our work provides insights on how to communicate with citizens, patients and professionals about research, risk and individual responsibility.

Our approach to teaching ethics

Students, scientists, professionals and decision-makers all experience ethical dilemmas. The Centre provides [ethics teaching and training](#) for undergraduate, master and PhD students at Uppsala University, and offers flexible training modules for staff. We provide tools to explore the values at stake and reflect on and manage ethical problems. We believe that good education rests on a solid foundation of research. Good teaching begins with the teacher's own knowledge and competence. Questions are at the core of training and education, with examination becoming an integrated part of learning. We aim to help students and colleagues develop their competence, allowing them to identify the values at stake when they are faced with ethical dilemmas in their professional life or research.

Exercises in critical thinking provide students with an opportunity to practice critical analysis and allow them to evaluate arguments for and against different opinions. For this reason, most of our teaching is interactive. We combine theoretical knowledge with practice and often start the discussion with actual cases and research ethics or medical ethics dilemmas. Our teaching combines theoretical knowledge with discussions of current real-life cases and questions that connect to students' everyday experiences.

Societal engagement

We take the third task of the University seriously and actively engage with stakeholders to build ethical competence, promote good research practice, and support the uptake of research results through tailored & targeted science communication.

Our research develops knowledge about **ethical competence** and contributes to understanding the values at stake. Our collaboration with the Region of Uppsala provides clinical ethics support for decision-makers and practitioners.

The Centre is instrumental in driving Uppsala University's work to develop **good research practice, research ethics & academic integrity**. Our efforts include generating knowledge about the laws, regulations and ethical guidelines that govern research, operationalised in our research efforts, education, link libraries, provision of expertise, guidance and information.

For many years, the Centre has made a coordinated effort to develop tools and channels for **science communication**. We use blogs and other channels to reflect on the impact of research and people's understanding of science. We also support uptake of research results with tailored science communication tools and tactics for different stakeholder groups, and lead efforts to communicate, disseminate and develop impact strategy in several European projects.

The Centre in numbers

In 2024, total funding for Centre activities amounted to 22 891 364 SEK (compared to 23 488 624 SEK in 2023). Centre funding provided by the disciplinary domains amounts to 2 708 000 SEK. In total, faculty funding for the research group amounts to 9 569 883 SEK, of which 2 426 595 SEK (25%) is funding related to the Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics; external research grants amount to 12 332 848 SEK (compared to 12 973 474 SEK in 2023); with 1 440 277 generated through undergraduate and graduate teaching.

With 28 employees and 11 associated researchers in 2024, CRB is by far the largest bioethics and research ethics research environment in Sweden, with a growing group of junior staff, currently consisting of five PhD students and one research assistant.

Translated to employee full-time equivalents, the Centre workforce comprises 22,2 staff, with externally funded researchers and postdocs making up the majority (43%). Two half-time senior lecturers were recruited to fill gaps in teaching, and both positions were filled in early 2024. With lecturers representing 14% of the total staff effort in 2024 (compared to only 3% in 2023). The Centre's teaching effort is supported by all staff members, including doctoral students and technical/administrative staff.

In addition to employees, the Centre's dynamic and multi-disciplinary senior research environment includes a substantial group of associated researchers (11), and the junior research community is strengthened by one external PhD student, employed by the Region of Sörmland.

Internal funding mechanisms

A large part of the Centre's funding is performance-based, generating a total of 2 691 472 SEK, representing a 9,5% increase compared to 2023. The largest increase is related to external funding, representing an improvement of 9,7% (to 1 274 430 SEK), whereas reimbursement for publications increased by 9% (to 742 326 SEK), while examination of students remained approximately the same (674 716 SEK). In 2024, 15 groups at the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences received performance-based faculty funding, with the Centre being the largest recipient: generating 22,8% of the total performance-based funding for the Department, representing a small increase (0,4%) compared to 2023.

Internal funding: 10 558 523

Another large portion of the Centre's budget is based on teaching. The Centre offers three master-level courses for 7,5 credits each at the Department of Public Health and Caring Sciences, covering Neuroethics, Ethics and Public Health & Ethics in Research, Writing and Communication. We are responsible for the ethics training in several programmes at Uppsala University, including the Medical doctor's programme; Nursing programme; Specialist nursing programme; Midwives programme; Engineering programme in molecular biotechnology; Teacher education in natural sciences and biology; Master's programme in public health; Master's programme in infection biology; Master's Programmes in forensic science, molecular medicine, precision medicine and innovative medicine.

In addition to teaching undergraduate and master-level students, we provide teaching for PhD students in medicine & pharmacy on research ethics (with around 70 students in 2024) and popular science writing (70 students in 2024), and research ethics for science & technology (around 90 students in 2024). CRB also ran a one-off course in research ethics for PhD students in caring science for Mälardalsområdets forskarskola i vårdvetenskap (30 students, including UU students). As part of our efforts for the disciplinary domains at Uppsala University, we also provide flexible training modules that have been used in courses for doctoral students in other disciplinary domains.

In addition, the Centre received a faculty contribution towards rent (968 816 SEK, representing a 7,7% increase since 2023) and a 300 000 contribution from the Centre for Medical Humanities graduate school for a PhD project on ethical dilemmas and ethical competence related to providing dietary advice.

Centre activities for disciplinary domains

The Centre received 2 708 000 from the three disciplinary domains as a foundation for the mission to provide research ethics teaching, initiate research and provide expertise. Funding increased by 9,8% from the previous year. Together with the research group and Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics, the centre provides critical mass and creates synergies, for example through the dual role

of Centre Director Stefan Eriksson, who also serves as an advisor to the Vice Chancellor on Good Research Practice; and leader of a group of confidants appointed by the disciplinary domains to provide support and advice, platforms for knowledge sharing and capacity building, training and advice on ethics review.

The Centre provides expertise and hands-on guidance for staff through modular training, and online resources for staff, providing information, tools, resources, and guidelines for different needs and aspects of ethics in research and academic practice. Until May 2024, the Centre also provided this information to external audiences through the Codex website (www.codex.uu.se), first developed in 2000 with support from the Swedish Research Council. However, as many actors are now providing online resources, the resource was integrated into the Uppsala University research handbook and is now available through the employee pages on Uppsala University's website.

Another long-term public online resource: The Ethics Blog and its Swedish-language counterpart Etikbloggen, have been publishing reflective content about research and research practice since 2011. The blog is published weekly and reaches around 7,000 email subscribers. With 939 posts since the start, a total of 62 posts were published in 2024 (31 on each blog).

The Centre's flexible training modules are currently being used in our courses and training, and other courses at Uppsala University (e.g. Forskningsetik och kommunikation at the Department of Modern Languages). They are also used in the national Research Ethics for Researchers in Medicine course (mandatory for future supervisors) developed jointly by all Universities that offer the medical doctor's programme.

The Centre organises a series of open higher seminars conducted jointly with the Stockholm Centre for Healthcare Ethics (CHE), a collaborative centre established by Karolinska Institutet, the Royal Institute of Technology, and Stockholm University. In 2024, the series included 19 seminars (compared to 22 in 2023) for staff and occasional guests to discuss and enhance unpublished work, primarily benefiting junior researchers by promoting academic discourse and skill development in a supportive setting. PhD students at the Centre earn academic credits for participating.

We share our expertise as invited speakers at conferences, reviewers, events and meetings organised by academia, government, and civil society; and engage in activities organised by other Departments at Uppsala University. In 2024, the Centre organised the largest annual Swedish conference on medical ethics, forming part of a series organised consecutively by medical ethics research environments at Lund University and Karolinska Institutet. The “UMEC” conference was held from 10-11 June 2024. The conference had 81 registered participants from universities across Europe, and from Africa and Australia, with 49 oral presentations including 3 keynote speakers.

Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics

The Chair in Clinical Medical Ethics includes research as well as teaching for the Medical doctor’s programme on the ethics of euthanasia, paediatric care, obstetric & gynaecological care, and priority setting in health care but also the teaching of doctoral students and healthcare professionals at Region Uppsala. 20% of the Chair’s salary is covered by a grant from Vetenskapsrådet (Just Severity). The 3-year temporary funding (etableringsbidrag) has been used to establish a platform for research on clinical medical ethics at the Centre through two projects: One PhD project that started in November 2022, where Adam Ehlert builds on this work by looking at severity as a priority setting criterion in healthcare. The other is establishing research in compulsory care. Both these projects have resulted in several articles and the latter in an anthology on compulsory care that was completed in late 2024 (published in Swedish February 2025): *Tvång på gott och ont – En forskningsantologi om tvång i välfärden*. These projects has also resulted in succesful research applications to Vetenskapsrådet that was granted funding during fall 2024: Just Pricing of Pharmaceuticals (JUPP) (where the Chair functions as PI) and Decision Competence as a Basis of Compulsory Care. Both these projects start in 2025 and runs for three years (the former covers 20% and the latter 15% of the Chair).

50% of the Professor’s chair in clinical medical ethics is funded by the Region of Uppsala, where the Professor chairs the regional Ethics Council, and provides advice in ethically difficult cases. The Ethics Council works to strengthen ethical competence in health care. The Council meets every two months to discuss ethical issues raised by either the Region’s healthcare sector or the

Council themselves, often covering more principal issues- In 2024, the council covered issues of principle, like to what extent the region should cover births at home on request from pregnant women. Mainly, the council addressed patient cases in case-based ethical support rounds, foremost at Akademiska hospital but also in primary care.

In addition to the Region of Uppsala, the Centre is collaborating with the Region of Sörmland, currently funding one PhD project on the transformation of family medicine and a research project on general practitioners' experiences of stress. Moreover, the regions Ethics Council has established cooperation with corresponding councils and networks in other regions, foremost in Dalarna, Gävleborg, Stockholm (Karolinska universitetssjukhuset), and Göteborg (Sahlgrenska sjukhuset).

External research funding

Research funding grants: 12 332 840 SEK

The majority of our research is funded through different European collaborative funding schemes. During 2024, we were involved in CAVAA (European Innovation Council); ConcePTION (Innovative Medicines Initiative); ENLIGHTENme (Horizon 2020); MINDtheGEPs (Horizon 2020); Neurotwin (Horizon 2020); and Screen4Care (Innovative Medicines Initiative); The Swedish Research Council is the second largest funding agency. In addition to the European collaborations funded through the ERA PerMed programme (RELIABLE, ONCOLOGICS & MEET-AML), we are also involved in the following projects funded directly by the Swedish Research Council: In the best interest of the child? (Swedish Research Council); Just Severity (Swedish Research Council); and Reviewing the Swedish Ethical Review Act (in Swedish *Sila mygg och svälja kameler?*, Swedish Research Council).

In 2024, the group was successful in several calls, with PIs from CRB winning money from several of the Swedish Research Council's calls: Humanities and Social Sciences in One Health: Promoting Just and Responsible Antibiotic Behaviour in Society; Just Pricing of Pharmaceuticals (JUPP). CRB researchers were also co-applicants in successful calls, receiving funding for projects on

Countering the Spread of AMR through Consumer Behaviour – Playing the AMR Card, led by the Department of Business Studies at Uppsala University and one project on decision making ability and coercive care (Beslutsförmåga och tvångsvård - juridik, etik och klinisk praktik när patienter motsätter sig vård) led by the Department of Law.

Projects funded by other agencies include AICare (WASP-HS); Providing dietary advice in primary care (Uppsala University, Centre for Medical Humanities); Public perceptions of cancer risk (Swedish Cancer Society); and RUBIKS: Ethical and clinical aspects of recruiting children with cancer to research (Swedish Childhood Cancer Society); and Ethical Analysis of Risk Communication Concerning Alcohol (Swedish Council for Information on Alcohol and Drugs – Systembolaget/CAN). During 2024, CRB researchers were also part of other successful project proposals, including a Forte-funded project on improving health promotion for people living in socioeconomically disadvantaged areas led by Umeå University; and a Wallenberg AI and Transformative Education Development Program (WASP-ED) project on integration of AI in the medical education, in collaboration between Uppsala University and Örebro University.

Communication & dissemination

We actively engage in debate and collaborate with stakeholders through both research activities and media. The Centre has a strong science communications profile, disseminating results through our website, X, Bluesky, two research blogs (Etikbloggen and The Ethics Blog), a Centre Zenodo community, and YouTube. The Centre's expertise on the impact and uptake of results plays an important role in research at the Centre. In 2024, we also led communication and dissemination efforts in two European projects: MINDtheGEPs (Horizon 2020), ConcePTION (Innovative Medicines Initiative). In addition to the Centre's website, we host websites for several ongoing and completed projects (H2020 SIENNA, H2020 MINDtheGEPs & IMI PREFER).

Discussions on the choice of social media platforms have been ongoing, in light of changes on the X platform. Close monitoring of the policy for X by Uppsala University, the Swedish Research Council, Innovative Health Initiative and Horizon Europe framework programme and assessment of our reach and engagement led to a decision to remain on X to ensure we are able to engage with EU-funded projects and stakeholders who are still active on the platform, and increase our presence on other platforms. Bluesky was chosen as an alternative social media platform to X. Our Bluesky handle was created on 26 November 2024, and since then, the account has gained an audience of 591 followers (27 February 2025). The account is listed in the Bioethics starterpack, which makes it easier for relevant users in the Bioethics community on Bluesky to find and follow our account.

Our outreach in numbers

In 2024, researchers at the Centre published 46 peer-reviewed publications (55 in 2023), with 46% reaching an Altmetric score over 10 (top 25%), compared to 42% in 2023. The highest score reached by a paper published in 2024 was 120, reached by a comment article in Nature Reviews Drug Discovery on public-private partnerships antimicrobial resistance¹; followed by 27, reached by a

¹ Fernow J., Olliver, M., Couet W. et al. (2025). The AMR Accelerator: from individual organizations to efficient antibiotic development partnerships. *Nature Reviews Drug Discovery*, 24, 1-2. DOI:10.1038/d41573-024-00138-9 (first online 23 September 2024)

publication about women's attitudes towards the use of AI in mammography². In 2023, the highest score was 682, reached by a publication about AI detection tools³. One year later, the score of this publication is 730, with the largest part of the score coming from 249 mentions on X. We were featured in public media discussions on, for example, ethics in higher education and research, integrity, artificial intelligence technology, maternity and neonatal care, [appearing in 17 media outlets](#) (10 in 2023). Sometimes interviewed as experts, and sometimes as authors of opinion texts.

The Centre's official website, www.crb.uu.se (www.uu.se/centre/crb from April 5, 2024), is an information hub for projects, publications, and personnel. It includes dynamic content such as the Ethics Blog feed and news from the Centre. Our blog posts and news items are shared on the CRB's X account (@crb_uu), with 757 followers (27 February 2025). In 2024, we published 184 posts on X, with a total of 19,765 impressions. Data on engagement rates requires paying for the X account, which means we have limited data. However, since the summer of 2024, we have noted a significant decrease in engagement without content on X, reflecting that many users from the bioethics research community have left the platform, and the algorithm has changed. However, we do get engagement with content from other segments of our audience who are still active on the platform.

Want to know more?

Web: www.uu.se/crb/

Blog: www.etikbloggen.crb.uu.se & www.ethicsblog.crb.uu.se

X: https://x.com/crb_uu

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/crb-uu.bsky.social>

Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/crb/>

YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@crb_uu

² Viberg Johansson, J., Dembrower, K., Strand, F., & Grauman, Å. (2024). Women's perceptions and attitudes towards the use of AI in mammography in Sweden: a qualitative interview study. *BMJ Open*, 14(2). DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2024-084014

³ Weber-Wulff, D., Anohina-Naumeca, A., Bjelobaba, S. et al. (2023). Testing of detection tools for AI-generated text. *International Journal for Educational Integrity*, 19(1). DOI: 10.1007/s40979-023-00146-z